

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

**WP7 – Information and data
governance, ethics,
technology, data catalogue
and quality support**

D7.12 Wiki page with description of tools and GITHUB repository

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Abstract

This deliverable provides an extensive description of the resources available online that support the application of the ConcePTION pipeline, building on previous Deliverable (D) 7.11¹. It includes documentation of the ConcePTION Common Data Model (CDM), links to the repositories of open source tools, and a list of publications which already implemented the pipeline.

All the resources available online have been compiled in the IMI-ConcePTION GitHub repository “ConcePTION Tools”, under the tab ‘wiki’. The wiki page is publicly available at <https://github.com/IMI-ConcePTION/ConceptionTools/wiki>. The suite of open-source tools described here is sustained by a community of developers.

The ConcePTION pipeline has expanded greatly, being adopted by Demonstration Projects using Real-World Data (Work Package (WP) 1 in ConcePTION) as well as numerous other studies.

Abbreviations

CDM	Common Data Model
WP	Work Package
D	Deliverable
ETL	Extract, Transform and Load
DP	Demonstration Project

¹ Thayer, D., Menon, K. B. and Gini, R. (2021) Wiki page with description of tools and GITHUB repository (D7.11). Zenodo. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5829464.

Description of the content on the wiki page

We set up a wiki page to bring together and describe the tools generated by ConcePTION in WP 7 (Information and data governance, ethics, technology, data catalogue and quality support), hereafter refers as the **ConcePTIONTools** wiki, publicly available in the following link <https://github.com/IMI-ConcePTION/ConceptionTools/wiki>. In Appendix 1, we have provided the version of the wiki page at the time of finalization of this deliverable. The wiki might be updated based on new developments.

Below, we briefly describe the content that can be found in detail on the **ConcePTIONTools** wiki:

1. ConcePTION Pipeline

The wiki briefly describes the ConcePTION pipeline, as represented by Figure 1. The pipeline was first introduced in Deliverables (D)7.5 by Dodd et al.² and D7.11 by Thayer et al.³

Figure 1. Graphical representation of the ConcePTION pipeline introduced in D7.5 and further detailed in D7.11

2. Documentation of the ConcePTION Common Data Model (CDM)

The landmark tool of the ConcePTION pipeline is the ConcePTION CDM. Detailed information on this CDM can be found in the wiki as well as in the publication by Thurin et al.⁴

3. ConcePTION Catalogue of data sources

The development of the ConcePTION Catalogue of data sources was described in D7.6 (Swertz et al.)⁵, D7.7 (Swertz et al.)⁶, D7.9 (Swertz et al.)⁷ and D7.10 (Swertz et al.)⁸. Further information can be found in the paper by Swertz et al.⁹

4. Tools to support Extraction, Transformation, and Load (ETL) of data sources to the ConcePTION CDM

We provide the links to access examples, educational material, and ETL documentation to operate with the ConcePTION CDM.

² Dodd C, Gini R, Sturkenboom M, Hoxhaj V, Hollestelle M, Thurin N, et al. Report on existing common data models and proposals for ConcePTION (D7.5). Zenodo; 2020 Nov.

³ 1. Thayer D, Menon KB, Gini R. Wiki page with description of tools and GITHUB repository (D7.11). Zenodo; 2021 Aug.

⁴ Thurin NH, Pajouheshnia R, Roberto G, et al. From Inception to ConcePTION: Genesis of a Network to Support Better Monitoring and Communication of Medication Safety During Pregnancy and Breastfeeding. *Clin Pharmacol Ther.* 2022;111(1):321-331. doi:10.1002/cpt.2476

⁵ Swertz M, de Andrade F, Cunningham M, Dodd C, Gini R, Holub P, et al. Prototype of FAIR data catalogue-1st (D7.6). Zenodo; 2020 Jul.

⁶ Swertz M, Hyde E, de Andrade F, Gini R, Pajouheshnia R, Sturkenboom M, et al. Prototype of FAIR data catalogue - 2nd (D7.7). Zenodo; 2021 Aug.

⁷ Swertz M, Hyde E, Cunningham M, Gini R. Test report for FAIR data catalogue (1st) (D7.9). Zenodo; 2021 Aug. .

⁸ Swertz M, Hyde E. Test report for FAIR data catalogue 2nd (D7.10). Zenodo; 2023 Jan.

⁹ Swertz M, van Enkevort E, Oliveira JL, et al. Towards an Interoperable Ecosystem of Research Cohort and Real-world Data Catalogues Enabling Multi-center Studies. *Yearb Med Inform.* 2022;31(1):262-272. doi:10.1055/s-0042-1742522

5. *INSIGHT tool for data quality checking*

Before starting a study using a ConcePTION CDM instance, data quality assessments need to be performed to ensure the conformance, plausibility, and fit-for-purpose of the data to be used. Detailed Level 1, 2, 3 data quality checks, aligned with the EMA quality framework were created by Hoxhaj et al¹⁰. In the wiki, we provide the links to the public GitHub repositories to access the INSIGHT tools.

6. *ConcePTION Pregnancy Algorithm*

A novel algorithm to identify pregnancy was designed based on Matcho et al.¹¹ to identify pregnancies episodes experienced in underlying population on ConcePTION CDM instances. In the wiki, we provide the link to the public GitHub repository.

7. *Open-source R functions to build and document study-specific scripts*

Several packages have been developed to support the operation of the ConcePTION pipeline on its several steps (Step T2, T3 and T4). In the wiki, we provide the links to access the R-functions.

8. *Repositories of studies using the ConcePTION pipeline*

In the wiki, we provide the links to access the repositories to various ConcePTION demonstration projects (DP): DP1-Gabapentinoids, DP2-Antidepressants, DP3-Multiple Sclerosis & Lupus, DP4 – Migraine and DP5-Breast Cancer.

9. *Peer-reviewed publications of studies based on the ConcePTION pipeline*

Several networks and collaborations have adopted the ConcePTION pipeline (ConcePTION, VAC4EU, and EU PE&PV). Therefore, a variety of publications using the pipeline are and will be available, serving as a proof of its utility. The list of publication can be found in the wiki. VAC4EU has also created courses for its members to train them on use of the ConcePTION pipeline.

¹⁰ Hoxhaj H, Andaur Navarro CL, Riera-Arnau J, Elbers R, Alsina Ema, Dodd C et al. INSIGHT: A Tool for Fit-for-Purpose Evaluation and Quality Assessment of Observational Data Sources for Real World Evidence on Medicine and Vaccine Safety medRxiv 2023.10.30.23297753; doi:<https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.10.30.23297753>

¹¹ Matcho A, Ryan P, Fife D, Gifkins D, Knoll C, Friedman A. Inferring pregnancy episodes and outcomes within a network of observational databases. *PLoS One*. 2018;13(2):e0192033. Published 2018 Feb 1. doi:[10.1371/journal.pone.0192033](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0192033)

Expected audience of the ConcePTIONTools wiki

The target audience of the wiki page is:

- Members of the ConcePTION Consortium utilizing the tools for conducting ConcePTION studies.
- Members of the collaborations and networks that have already adopted the pipeline.
- Researchers interested in applying the ConcePTION pipeline to their own studies.

The wiki consists of concise introductions for each section followed by a series of links directing to relevant resources. Its minimalist design emphasizes self-contained resources, maintaining efficiency and clarity.

Evolution of the ConcePTIONTools wiki

In the previous version of this wiki documented in D7.11 by Thayer et al¹², we proposed to store all the R functions applicable to the ConcePTION pipeline in a single R package. This approach has shown to be unsustainable as multiple groups have developed different functions and merging them into a single package has proven unfeasible.

In this version (D7.12) instead, the **ConcePTIONTools** wiki works as a single entry point for all the necessary resources to operate using the ConcePTION pipeline, beyond a list of R functions.

Conclusion

The ConcePTION pipeline was developed after a thorough review of available CDMs and based on years of experience using CDMs in Europe. The ConcePTION CDM tables resemble the OMOP CDM tables, but do not require semantic harmonization. In the ConcePTION pipeline, semantic harmonization is conducted as part of the study script, which makes onboarding of data sources faster, and semantic harmonization transparent. The ConcePTION pipeline is adopted by multiple real world evidence networks such as the EU Pharmacoepidemiology & Pharmacovigilance Research Network (EU PE&PV), the SIGMA consortium and the Vaccine Monitoring Collaboration for Europe (VAC4EU) international association. These communities develop functionalities, code lists and trainings for their members.

This wiki we have made all public resources available for researchers in the **ConcePTIONTools** wiki, serving as an entry point to operationalize the ConcePTION pipeline. We expect that further resources will also be made available on this wiki upon release.

¹² Thayer, D., Menon, K. B. and Gini, R. (2021) Wiki page with description of tools and GITHUB repository (D7.11). Zenodo. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5829464

Appendix 1: content of the wiki

ConceptionTools

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Introduction

The [IMI-ConcePTION Project](#) has created a pipeline to conduct pharmacoepidemiology studies based on real-world data sources. To this date, the pipeline has been used in [multiple studies](#) conducted by several European networks. The pipeline can be used to study use and safety of medicines in pregnancy and lactation, or for a vast range of different research questions.

This wiki documents the resources available online to adopt and apply the ConcePTION pipeline.

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The ConcePTION pipeline

The ConcePTION pipeline represents the pathway of data transformations from original data to the figure and tables displaying results of a study as a sequence of 5 steps. The pipeline was first introduced in [Deliverable 7.5](#) based on a paper by [Gini and colleagues](#), and further detailed in [Deliverable 7.11](#).

The pipeline foresees 6 types of data (D1, ..., D6) and 5 steps of transformations between them (T1, ..., T5). This is a graphical representation of the pipeline

The steps are as follows

- D1 - Original data: this is the original data source, collected for purposes non necessarily including research
- T1 - Extract Transform and Load (ETL): this is the process of extracting from D1 an instance and converting it to a Common Data Model; in the IMI-ConcePTION project we use the ConcePTION CDM

- D2 - Common Data Model: this is the result of the conversion
- T2 - Create study variables: when a study protocol is specified, variables are derived from the CDM
- D3 - Study variables: datasets containing the study subjects (pregnancies, persons, ...) and their study variables, as needed to enact the study protocol.
- T3 - Apply study design: select, censor, match, ... as requested by the study protocol to create the analytic dataset
- D4 - Analytic dataset: dataset ready to enter descriptive or statistical analysis
- T4 - Data analysis: descriptive or statistical analysis
- D5 - Results: dataset storing the results of the data analysis
- T5 - Visualization: creation of figures and tables
- D6 - Figures and tables

In the pipeline, all the data D1, D2, D3 and D4 are stored at the premises of the Data Access Partners (DAPs). T1 is programmed by the programmers of the DAP, while T2, T3 and T4 are included in a common program, The data D5 are shared in a secure environment.

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ConcePTION Common Data Model documentation

The ConcePTION Common Data Model (CDM) was introduced in [Deliverable 7.5](#) and published in the paper by Thurin and colleagues, available at [this link](#). It is the currently used D2 in the [ConcePTION pipeline](#), but the pipeline may also be applied to other CDM

The ConcePTION CDM version 2.2. is documented as follows - data tables at [this link](#) - vocabulary at [this link](#) - suggestions to the vocabulary at [this link](#)

A simulated instance of the ConcePTION CDM is available [at this link](#).

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ConcePTION Catalogue of data sources

The ConcePTION Catalogue of data sources was described in [this deliverable](#) and in the paper by Swertz and colleagues available at [this link](#).

It can be accessed [at this link](#) upon registration. Registration is currently restricted to members of the ConcePTION Consortium.

It describes the original data sources (D1 in the [ConcePTION pipeline](#)) available to conduct studies.

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Tools to support Extract, Transform and Load of data sources to the ConcePTION CDM

The process to Extract, Transform and Load (ETL) a data source to the ConcePTION CDM (T1 in the [ConcePTION pipeline](#)) is [described with videos and slides that can be accessed in this folder](#).

A template of the ETL Documentation Document is available [at this link](#), and a completed example is [at this link](#).

The requirements for a script executing the ETL design are described [at this link](#).

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Data quality checks - INSIGHT tool

Two suites of level checks are available before starting any study on an instance of the ConcePTION CDM.

- [INSIGHT Level 1](#) to assess the integrity of the ETL process from an original instance of a data source to a ConcePTION CDM instance, to provide feedback on the integrity of the ETL, and to produce high-level characterization of the data
- [INSIGHT Level 2](#) to assess internal consistency both within and between tables of the ConcePTION CDM instance
- [INSIGHT Level 3](#) A third suite can be used to support feasibility of a study by producing high-level characterization data tailored to the research question

A paper by Hoxhaj et al. describing the level checks is pre-printed and can be found [in this link](#)

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ConcePTION Pregnancy Algorithm

An updated algorithm was designed based on the work of Matcho et al. available at [this link](#) to create an algorithm to identify pregnancies in real world data sources that can be tailored to the specifics of each data source. The algorithm is available [in this repository](#).

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Open source functions to build and document study scripts

Multiple open-source functions are available to support studies conducted with the [ConcePTION pipeline](#)

- **packages to retrieve records from the data (step T2)**
 - [CreateConceptSetDatasets](#): this function retrieves records based on lists of codes (concept sets). It inspects a set of input tables of data and creates a group of datasets, each corresponding to a concept set. Each dataset contains the records of the input tables that match the corresponding concept set and is named out of it.
 - [CreateItemsetDatasets](#): this function retrieves records based on list of strings (item sets). It inspects a set of input tables of data and creates a group of datasets, each corresponding to a item set. Each dataset contains the records of the input tables that match the corresponding item set and is named out of it.
- **packages to process records recordwise, or across records of the same subject (step T2)**

- [MergeFilterAndCollapse](#): this function accesses a dataset containing one observation per unit of observation that is to be merged with one or more longitudinal datasets. The result is then filtered per some conditions (eg on the timeframe of the longitudinal observations), and then, as an option, collapsed to obtain again one record per unit of observation.
- [CreateSpells](#): this function takes as input a dataset with multiple time windows per unit of observation. Multiple categories of time windows may be recorded per unit, and time windows of the same unit may overlap, even within the same category. The purpose of the function is to create a dataset where the time windows of each person and category are disjoint (i.e., spells)
- **packages to inspect components of a same variable (step T2)**
 - [ApplyComponentStrategy](#): this function takes as input a dataset where component algorithms have been assigned, and the instructions to build composite algorithms based on them. It produces a dataset where the composites have been calculated, and a dataset where the overlap of selected pairs of algorithms is computed
- **packages to produce analytic datasets (step T3)**
 - [CreateFlowChart](#): this function applies exclusion criteria to a dataset of persons and produces the study population, as well as a dataset of counts of the impact of each exclusion criterion.
 - [CountPersonTime](#): this function splits the person time of each person, discards person time that is outside of the study period, and labels the remaining period with calendar years (or months or days) according to (possibly time-dependent) categorical variables; moreover, it computes person time per each of the events of interest, by applying censoring after the first occurrence of the event, and indicates whether an event is observed; finally, it counts events; the output can be individual or aggregated.
 - [CountPrevalence](#): this function is meant to be used in studies where point and/or period prevalence of one or more conditions, or prevalence of use of a medicinal product, need to be computed in multiple points or spans of times (years, or months, ...), possibly across strata of categorical variables such as age band and/or sex.
- **packages to produce archives of results (step T4)**
 - [Cube](#): this function takes as input a dataset with measures labelled with a combination of the minimum levels of a set of predefined dimensions. A *dimension* is a set of variables in hierarchical order. The set of variables in a dimension are called its *levels*. The function applies summary statistics (sum, mean, ...) to specified numeric columns. Summary statistics are computed over all the permutations of all levels of the dimensions, thus generating partial statistics.
- **tools to support study script development and documentation**
 - [CreateDAG](#): this is a set of functions (in the future a package) which aims to document the flow of a study script. It transform a spreadsheet containing name of scripts and their input and output datasets (index of the script) to a DAG in XML format, understood by the software draw.io (now reachable to diagrams.net). After importing the diagram to draw.io, it can be modified in a GUI

and exported as an image or HTML. Additional functionalities are under development, including the ability to link name of the scripts to the actual code in a GitHub repository, and to read codebooks of the input/output datasets to transform them in html pages, also linked to the the diagram. A prototype of this representation is available at [this link](#) for the [Covid Vaccine Monitoring](#) study.

The following packages are currently under development

- [CreateDaysOfTreatment](#): this function takes as input a dataset containing longitudinal records of prescriptions or dispensings, alongside with other information (e.g., Defined Daily Dose (DDD)), and a 'recipe' of choice of the investigator. The output of CreateDoT is a new variable containing the number of days of treatment prescribed/dispensed, per individual prescription/dispensing record.
- [GenerateMatchedDataset](#): this function takes as input at least two datasets, main_input and candidate_matches, each listing units of observations just once. It generates pairwise combinations of the units of observations, matched on a number of criteria, which may or may not involve time. A limited number of pairs per each unit of observation of main_input may be specified, or the complete set of pairs may be generated, if requested and if memory allows.

Other functions to work with the pipeline are developed and available through VAC4EU

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Repositories of studies using the ConcePTION Pipeline

- ConcePTION Demonstration Projects
 - [Demonstration Project 1](#)
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 - [Demonstration Project 3](#)
 - [Demonstration Project 4](#) (access currently restricted)
 - [Demonstration Project 5](#) (access currently restricted)
- VAC4EU repositories
 - [Early Covid Vaccine Monitoring](#)
 - [Covid Vaccine Monitoring](#)
 - [Covid Vaccines Effectiveness](#)
- CONSIGN project
 - [COVID-19 infection and medicines in pregnancy](#)
- EU PE & PV Research Network
 - [Risk minimization measures for Valproates](#)
 - [Risk minimization measures for Retinoids](#)

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Published studies based on the ConcePTION pipeline

- Hurley E, Geisler BP, Lupattelli A, Poblador-Plou B, Lassalle R, Jové J, et al. COVID-19 and pregnancy: A European study on pre- and post-infection medication use. Eur J Clin Pharmacol. 2024 Feb 12. doi: 10.1007/s00228-024-03639-z.

- Abtahi S, Pajouheshnia R, Durán CE, Riera-Arnau J, Gamba M, Alsina E, et al. Impact of 2018 EU Risk Minimisation Measures and Revised Pregnancy Prevention Programme on Utilisation and Prescribing Trends of Medicinal Products Containing Valproate: An Interrupted Time Series Study. *Drug Saf.* 2023 Jun 9; <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC10252161/>
- Bots SH, Riera-Arnau J, Belitser SV, Messina D, Aragón M, Alsina E, et al. Myocarditis and pericarditis associated with SARS-CoV-2 vaccines: A population-based descriptive cohort and a nested self-controlled risk interval study using electronic health care data from four European countries. *Frontiers in Pharmacology.* 2022;13. Available from: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fphar.2022.1038043>
- Durán CE, Riera-Arnau J, Abtahi S, Pajouheshnia R, Hoxhaj V, Gamba M, et al. Impact of the 2018 revised Pregnancy Prevention Programme by the European Medicines Agency on the use of oral retinoids in females of childbearing age in Denmark, Italy, Netherlands, and Spain: an interrupted time series analysis. *Front Pharmacol.* 2023;14:1207976. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC10469888/>
- Riefolo F, Castillo-Cano B, Martín-Pérez M, Messina D, Elbers R, Brink-Kwakkel D, et al. Effectiveness of homologous/heterologous booster COVID-19 vaccination schedules against severe illness in general population and clinical subgroups in three European countries. *Vaccine.* 2023 Oct 17; Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0264410X23011817>
- Sturkenboom M, Messina D, Paoletti O, Burgos-Gonzalez A de, García-Poza P, Huerta C, et al. Cohort monitoring of 29 Adverse Events of Special Interest prior to and after COVID-19 vaccination in four large European electronic healthcare data sources. *medRxiv*; 2022. p. 2022.08.17.22278894. Available from: <https://www.medrxiv.org/content/10.1101/2022.08.17.22278894v1>
- Willame C, Dodd C, Durán C, Elbers R, Gini R, Bartolini C, et al. Background rates of 41 Adverse Events of Special Interest for COVID-19 vaccines in 10 European healthcare databases - An ACCESS cohort study. *Vaccine.* 2022 Nov 22; Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0264410X22014293>.

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Publicly available reports based on the ConcePTION pipeline for EMA funded projects

- Durán, C. E., Messina, D., Gini, R., Riefolo, F., Aragón, M., Belitser, S., Bissacco, C. A., Bots, S. H., de Burgos, A., Carreras-Martínez, J. J., Correcher-Martínez, E., Douglas, I., Garcia-Poza, P., Girardi, A., Herings, R., Hoxhaj, V., Huerta, C., Hyeraci, G., Ientile, V., ... Sturkenboom, M. (2023). Rapid Safety Assessment of SARS-CoV-2 Vaccines in EU Member States using Electronic Health Care Data Sources (COVID Vaccine Monitor-CVM study): Final Study Report for WP3 (electronic health record data). Lessons Learned about Methods of Monitoring COVID-19 Vaccine Safety., Utrecht, the Netherlands. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10093613>
- Martín-Merino, E., Riefolo, F., Vaz, T., Grimaldi, L., & Gini, R. (2023). Covid Vaccines Effectiveness (CoVE) Effectiveness of heterologous and booster COVID-19 vaccination in 5 European countries, using a cohort approach in children and adults with a full

primary COVID-19 vaccination regimen. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7858776>

- Sturkenboom, M., Messina, D., Paoletti, O., de Burgos, A., Garcia, P., Huerta Álvarez Consuelo, Llorente, A., Klungel, O., Martin, M., Martinez, M., Martin, I., Overbeek, J., Souverein, P., Swart, K., & Gini, R. (2022). Cohort monitoring of Adverse Events of Special Interest and COVID-19 diagnoses prior to and after COVID-19 vaccination (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6762311>
- Willame, C., Dodd, C., Gini, R., Durán, C., Thomsen, R., Wang, L., Gedebjerg, A., Kahlert, J., Ehrenstein, V., Bartolini, C., Droz, C., Moore, N., Haug, U., Schink, T., Diez-Domingo, J., Mira-Iglesias, A., Vergara-Hernández, C., Carreras, J., Villalobos, F., ... Sturkenboom, M. (2021). Background rates of Adverse Events of Special Interest for monitoring COVID-19 vaccines (2.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5255870>
- Hurley, E., Sturkenboom, M., Poblador-Plou, B., Sanfelix-Gimeno, G., Sanchez, F., Hurtado, I., Rodriguez, C., Jordan, S., Thayer, D., Scanlon, I., Bartolini, C., Limoncella, G., Gini, R., & Nordeng, H. (2021). COVID-19 infection and medicines in pregnancy – a multinational registry based study Medication use in pregnant women with COVID-19: an interim report. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5775644>
- Hurley, E., Sturkenboom, M., Nordeng, H., & CONSIGN consortium. (2023). COVID-19 infection and medicines in pregnancy – a multinational electronic health records/registry-based study. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091496>
- Sturkenboom, M., Klungel, O., Durán, C. E., Riera-Arnau, J., Abtahi, S., Pajouheshnia, R., Hoxhaj, V., Gamba, M., Dodd, C., Alsina, E., Martin-Perez, M., Garcia-Poza, P., Llorente-Garcia, A., Gonzalez-Bermejo, D., Ibáñez, L., Sabaté, M., Vidal, X., Ballarín, E., Sanfélix-Gimeno, G., ... Erikstrup-Hallgreen, C. (2023). Impact of EU Label Changes and Revised Pregnancy Prevention Programme for Oral Retinoid-Containing Medicinal Products: acitretin, alitretinoin and isotretinoin (2.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8317445>
- Klungel, O., Sturkenboom, M., Abtahi, S., Pajouheshnia, R., Durán Salinas, C., Riera Arnau, J., Dodd, C., Gardarsdottir, H., Souverein, P., Hoxhaj, V., Siiskonen, S. J., Gamba, M., Alsina, E., Huerta, C., Bermejo, D. G., Corominas, D. M., Martín-Pérez, M., Garcia-Poza, P., García, A. L., ... Lely, T. (2022). Impact of EU label changes and revised pregnancy prevention programme for medicinal products containing valproate: utilisation and prescribing trends (v3.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7074588>
- Sturkenboom, M., Messina, D., Paoletti, O., de Burgos, A., Garcia, P., Huerta Álvarez Consuelo, Llorente, A., Klungel, O., Martin, M., Martinez, M., Martin, I., Overbeek, J., Souverein, P., Swart, K., & Gini, R. (2022). Cohort monitoring of Adverse Events of Special Interest and COVID-19 diagnoses prior to and after COVID-19 vaccination (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6762311>

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